

EJP SOIL
ARTEMIS

**Towards climate-smart sustainable management of
agricultural soils**

ARTEMIS

Deliverable 2.2 & 2.3

AE systems yield stability under climatic stress

Identifying drivers of yield stability

Due date of deliverable: M57

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D2.2: Report on the performance of specific AE systems in different European pedoclimatic regions with respect to yield stability in years of climatic stress

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D2.3 Identifying drivers of yield stability

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1. Introduction

1.1. Aim of this report

Crop yield and yield stability stand as crucial indicators of agricultural productivity and sustainability, central to addressing the escalating global food demand alongside the challenges posed by climate change (Olesen et al., 2011). Notably, yield stability, defined as a crop's ability to produce consistent yields across various environments and over multiple growing seasons, has gained in interest since the increased variability of climate is also associated with a decreased stability of crop yields. As farmers face more frequent and unpredictable extreme climate events, including droughts, floods, and heat waves, the capability to achieve both high and stable yields under climatic stresses is essential for maintaining food security and economic predictability (Müller et al., 2018).

Soils play a vital role in providing various ecosystem services that contribute to both mitigation and adaptation to climate change, and land management practices significantly influence the ability of soils to deliver these services. Agroecological (AE) systems, in particular, have gained increased attention for their potential to enhance resilience against climate extremes while delivering crucial ecosystem services. Despite the recognition that AE systems often yield less than conventional practices, studies suggest their increased resilience under environmental stress (Lichtfouse, 2012). This resilience may enable these AE systems to better withstand the pressures of a changing climate. However, comprehensive evaluations of AE systems focusing specifically on yield performance and yield stability during extreme climatic events remain scarce.

Long-term field experiments (LTEs) offer unique opportunities to assess the long-term effects of various cropping systems and management practices, particularly concerning time-dependent parameters such as yield stability. Indeed, these experiments provide long-term data and observations that allow for the analysis of yearly variability in crop performance under fluctuating environmental conditions.

The tasks T2.3 and T2.3 of the EJP SOIL “ARTEMIS” project aim to identify agroecosystems with increased yield stability and to deepen our understanding of how specific AE practices influence soil ecosystem service indicators driving yield stability.

To reach these objectives, the differences in yield and yield stability between AE and conventional farming systems, particularly regarding their resilience during periods of climatic stress, were evaluated in regionally representative field experiments across Europe. These experiments allow for context and system-specific analysis of data as the implementation of AE practices and their effects on soil properties are very often context specific.

Specifically, this research investigates the influences of panel of farming systems (conventional and organic), combined agroecological practices, soil and crop management practices including the management of crop rotations, crop protection, various tillage methods, organic/mineral fertilisation, covering of the soil, incorporation of crop residues on yield levels and stability. Data from local meteorological stations close to the LTEs were used to identify cropping seasons under climatic stress in order to quantify their effects compared to normal years and in relation to the treatments investigated in each LTE. Although statistical approaches may vary to

accommodate local conditions, a common definition of yield stability has been established at the project's outset to enable meaningful comparisons in the future.

Thus, this study not only addresses vital agronomic questions but also contributes to the broader discourse on sustainable agricultural practices capable of meeting future food security challenges.

This present report provides a synthesis of the material & methods, results and discussion sections derived from the individual studies conducted by the ARTEMIS project partners. More detailed informations can be found in the attached six individual reports.

1.2. Background

In the review article of Reckling et al. 2021, a methodological guide has been proposed to aid in the evaluation of yield stability in agricultural Long-Term Experiments, focusing on the following topics : (1) data quality, (2) outliers, (3) confounding factors, (4) detrending, (5) temporal autocorrelation, (6) choice of stability measure, (7) dependance of stability measures on the mean, (8) temporal trends of stability and (9) standard errors of statistical inference of stability measures.

Currently there are no commonly accepted guidelines or consensus for assessing yield stability in LTEs. The selection of particular stability measures is often based on personal or disciplinary preferences rather than systematic knowledge about the properties and suitability of particular indices. Thus it is crucial to be familiar with and employ knowledge regarding the strengths and weaknesses of various stability measures in order to effectively assess the impact of agronomic systems or other factors on stability.

There are two main contrasting concepts of stability commonly used in plant breeding context : (1) the static and (2) the dynamic concept. According to the static concept, the most stable genotype maintains a constant yield across environments while according to the dynamic concept for a stable genotype implies a yield response having a constant difference to the mean response of all tested genotypes in each environment. There are two primary types of stability measures : regression- and variance-based measures. Additionally, there are two available analysis methods for studying stability: the GGE (Genotype plus genotype-by-environment) biplot analysis available or the AMMI (Additive Main effects and Multiplicative Interactions) analysis-based stability indexes.

It is known that some indices have, though independently developed, are in fact mathematically equivalent, while other pairs of indices seem to correlate strongly. Still, the interpretation of the results is often difficult because different stability measures may lead to contrasting conclusions, partly because they reflect different concepts of stability. Moreover, the choice of stability index has to be specific to the LTE since they are characterized by a number of typical issues that affect stability analysis in specific ways: length of the experiment, changes in management during the course of the experiment, temporal autocorrelation, strong temporal trends of yields, data gaps that need to be dealt appropriately in the statistical analyses.

2. Material and methods

2.1. General description of the six long-term experiments

Seven long-term experiments (LTE)s managed by 6 partners institutions in four countries have been selected for the processing of the yield stability analyses in ARTEMIS project. The countries have been highlighted in the map of Fig. 1. These LTEs cover a diversified range of pedoclimatic areas of Europe. A south to north gradient was obtained with contrasted types of climates: mediterranean, continental and temperate. Their main characteristics have been reported in Table 1.

Fig. 1. Localisation of the seven LTEs that were analysed in four countries (in yellow)

Table 1. Main characteristics of the seven LTEs used in this study

LTE name	Country	Region	City	Latitude (N)	Longitude (E)	Elevation (m)	Soil type	Est. date
----------	---------	--------	------	-----------------	------------------	------------------	-----------	--------------

Agris	Italia	Sardinia	San Michele	39.42	9.02	99	Inceptisol with vertic characteristics and Alfisol	2003
MITIORG	Italia	Basilicata	Metaponto	40.40	16.80	8	Clayey and poorly drained, Typic epiaquerts	2014
DOK	Switzerland	Bâle-Campagne	Therwil	47.50	7.54	308	Haplic luvisol on deep deposits of alluvial loess	1978
Borovce	Slovakia	Trnava	Piešťany	48.58	17.73	174	Luvi-Haplic Chernozem	1974
LTE-OM	Belgium	Wallonia	Gembloux	50.56	4.73	167	Hortic luvisol on deep deposits of alluvial loess	1959
LTE-Tillage	Belgium	Wallonia	Gembloux	50.66	4.73	167	Hortic luvisol on deep deposits of alluvial loess	2005
BOPACT	Belgium	Flanders	Gent	50.99	3.77	24	Bathygleyic cambisol	2010

Here is a summary of the different agricultural practices, the corresponding levels of treatments/factors as well as the specific crops evaluated in the eight LTEs :

1. **Agris** : This trial investigates three types of tillage systems:

- Conventional Tillage: Traditional plowing methods.
- Reduced Tillage: Less soil disturbance compared to conventional methods.
- No Tillage (sod seeding)

Additionally, it tests two different crop rotations, including continuous wheat and a legumes-wheat rotation, with durum wheat as the evaluated crop. This experiment has a special feature of being replicated in two sites that are located about 1 km from each other (Benatzu and Ussana).

2. **MITIORG** : This experiment was designed to adapt local organic vegetables systems to extreme winter rainfall events with the adoption of ridge-furrow system (soil surface shaping) and the combination of other AE practices :

in ridges :

- Introduction of cover crops (burr medic or crimson clover) or not
- Organic fertilisation : Comparison of commercial organic fertilizers and on-farm compost, against a control.

In flat strips :

- Termination methods of cover crops are compared: ploughed in as green manure, flattened with a roller crimper and no cover crops

- Organic fertilisation : Comparison of commercial organic fertilizers and on-farm compost, against a control.

The vegetable crops evaluated include cauliflower, fennel, tomato, zucchini, and lettuce.

3. **DOK** : This trial evaluates two farming systems, comparing conventional and organic practices with two levels of fertilisation : Half and full

Four crops are assessed in this trial : potato, soybean, winter wheat, and maize.

4. **Borovce** : This experiment tests different proportion of cereals in crop rotation, varying among: 40%, 60% and 80%.

Additionally, two types of fertilisation are compared : mineral vs mineral and organic

The crop evaluated in this trial is winter wheat.

5. **LTE-OM** : The focus of this trial is organic fertilisation, comparing: mineral Control, pig slurry and cattle manure. It also examines the incorporation or not of crop residues and the use of cover crops or not. Three crops are evaluated: sugar beet, winter wheat, and winter barley.

6. **LTE-Tillage** : This trial assesses three types of tillage systems: Conventional Tillage, non-inversion tillage and reduced tillage. The experiment also includes crop protection treatments, specifically the use of fungicides (applied or not). Two crops are evaluated sugar beet and winter wheat.

7. **BOPACT**: This trial explores two types of slurries (cattle vs pig), two tillage systems (conventional vs non-inversion tillage and the application of compost or not).

The following crops are evaluated : potato, maize, spring barley and fodder beet.

2.2. Stability indicators used

Currently, there exists a list of 42 stability indices. As mentioned above, the selection of yield stability indices has to be specific to the LTEs since their characteristics and typical issues can vary a lot. At least the coefficient of variation (CV) was the minimal common stability indicator calculated by each partner.

The CV normalizes the absolute variability of yield data (i.e., standard deviation (SD)) relative to the mean yield, so the CV is defined as the ratio of the standard deviation to the mean. This indicator presents the advantage of being independent of the unit in which the measurement was taken. Thus, this indicator can be used to compare data sets with different units or widely different means. As a percentage (Equation 1), CV allows for direct comparisons of variability across trials with different mean yields, providing a more standardized measure of stability. Furthermore, this measurement is easy to interpret : a high CV indicates the yields in the specific group/treatment/crop is more variable, whereas a low value indicates a lower variability and

thus higher yield stability. A low CV is desirable in agricultural systems where consistency and crop performance predictability is key. The CV is calculated as follows:

$$CV = \left(\frac{\sigma}{\mu}\right) \times 100 \quad (1)$$

where:

- σ is the standard deviation of the data set.
- μ is the mean of the data set.
- The result is multiplied by 100 to express the CV as a percentage.

Given the partly large differences in the design, assessment of parameters and availability of data, the determination of yield stability partly varied between the different LTEs involved in this research activity. We provide an overview about the computed indicators of yield stability in Table 2.

Table 2. Summary table of stability indicators evaluated in each LTE

Yield stability indicator			Long-term field experiments						
Name	Acronym	Nr in review of Reckling (2021)	Original source	1 Northern Belgium (Gent, Flanders)	2 Southern Belgium (Gembloux, Wallonia)	3 Western Switzerland (Therwil, Bâle-Campagne)	4 Southern Italia (Metaponto, Basilicata)	5 Western Italia (Sardinia)	6 Western Slovakia (Piešťany, Trnava)
Coefficients of variation (CV)	CV	#1	Francis & Kannenberg (1978) Can J Plant Sci 58: 1029-1034	x	x	x	x	x	x
Kang's rank-sum statistic	-		Kang (1988)						x
Relative stability ratios	-		-original indicator-			x			
Scale-adjusted coefficient of variation	aCV	#4	Döring & Reckling (2018) Eur J Agron 99: 33-36		x		x	x	
(Wricke's) Ecovalence	Wi	#7	Plaisted & Peterson (1959) Am Pot J 36: 381-385		x		x	x	
Yield stability index	YSI	#42	Bacsi & Hollosy (2019) Analecta Technica Szegedinensia 13: 11-20.				x	x	
AMMI Based Stability Parameter	ASTAB							x	
AMMI stability index	ASI							x	

AMMI stability value	ASV	#22	Fikere et al. (2014): Afr J Agr Res 33: 2574-2583		x
Modified AMMI stability index	MASI				x
Modified AMMI stability value	MASV				x
Weighted Average of Absolute Scores for AMMI analysis	WAAS				x
Regression coefficient against environmental mean	b	#9	Finlay & Wilkinson (1963) Austr J Agr Res 14: 742-754	x	
Power Law Residuals	POLAR	#16	Döring et al. (2015) Field Crops Res 183: 294-302	x	
Safety first index / Production risk	P	#30	Eskridge (1990) Crop Sci 30: 369-374	x	
Coefficient of determination (of linear regression against environmental means)	R ²	#13	Pinthus (1973) Euphytica 22: 121-123	x	
Deviation mean squares / Deviation from regression	S ² d	#10	Eberhard & Russell (1966) Crop Sci 6: 36-40	x	
Environmental variance			Römer (1917)	x	
Hanson's genotypic stability parameter / genotypic stability	D ²	#17	Hanson (1970) Theor Appl Genet 40: 226-231	x	

Genotypic / Cultivar superiority measure	Pi	#19	Lin & Binns (1988) Can J Plant Sci 68: 193-198	x	
Variance of rank	Si	#23	Nassar & Huehn 1987. Biometrics. 43: 45-53	x	
Stability variance / Shukla's stability variance	σ^2	#5	Shukla (1972) Hered 28: 237-245	x	x

3. Results

3.1. Crop management, agroecological systems and their influence on crop yield stability : summary of the main results of country specific report

3.1.1. Comparison of farming systems

In Switzerland, the analyses showed that yield stability was generally increased in the conventional farming systems compared to the organic farming system in both years with “normal” and “extreme” climate conditions, especially at half fertilisation, across most of the crops. The largest difference between the farming systems in terms of relative yield stability were observed for the crops potatoes and maize. The only significant advantage for organic systems was observed at full fertilization at soybean in both climate scenarios. This suggests that organic systems mainly can close the yield gap in scenarios when nutrient limitations are less severe.

Climatic conditions had varying effects on both systems, but conventional systems generally demonstrated better resilience to climatic stress, certainly due to more robust nutrient management practices.

Interestingly, winter wheat yields were unaffected by climatic stress, regardless of the system, with organic yields even outperforming conventional ones in some cases (98% of conventional yields during stress events). This may suggest that winter wheat is more resilient to climate fluctuations or that organic management practices favour winter wheat under stress conditions.

3.1.2. Comparison of soil management practices

Tillage & organic matter managements (slurry, compost)

In Belgium-Flanders, the analysis revealed that climatic conditions, particularly drought and extreme rainfall, significantly influenced both yield and yield stability of maize and spring barley (crops that were planted during years that climatic extremes were identified). However, no significant effects of the tested treatments / factors, or their interactions on yield stability were detected.

This lack of response suggests that the specific treatments tested do not significantly influence crop's availability to withstand variability of climate. Furthermore, while certain practices (e.g. the use of cattle rather than pig slurry) may enhance yield of winter barley under optimal conditions, their effectiveness may diminish during periods of climatic stress.

Organic matter management (crop residues, farmyard manure, slurry, cover crops)

In the first LTE of Belgium-Wallonia (OM), the applications of livestock manures had a more pronounced effect on yields, especially for winter cereals (wheat and barley), whereas the effects of crop residues and cover crops were not significant. Throughout the overall experimental period, yield stability remained unaffected by any treatments. Interestingly, climatic stress events (extreme drought, rainfalls, heat) affected both yield and yield stability. These effects were also more pronounced on crop yield rather than on yield stability.

In terms of yield, the effect size of the stresses were in descending order : a depressive effect of wet cropping seasons on winter wheat, positive effects of drought on winter cereals and heat on all evaluated crops. Additionally, comparisons of treatment effects between normal and climate-stressed growing seasons indicated that the application of livestock manures allowed to reach relatively higher yields for winter barley compared to mineral fertilized plots in hot and drought years. However, in drought years, only the use of pig slurry led to significantly higher yields while the application of cattle manures showed no such effect.

Regarding yield stability, the influence of the treatments under climate stress was not significant. Our findings presented opposite outcomes under drought and heat stresses, with higher yield stability in one case and a lower stability in the other case. These results suggest that the application of livestock manures contributes to a more resilient cropping system under climate-stressed conditions.

Tillage & crop protection

In the second LTE of Belgium-Wallonia (tillage), while the effects of soil tillage was found to be not significant, the crop protection factor was significant for winter wheat, with anticipated increased crop yields in plots where fungicides were applied. Throughout the overall experimental period, yield stability remained unaffected by any treatments. In this experiment that started in 2005, few observations with climatic stress prevented to test the climate effects.

Tillage & crop rotations

In Italia (Sardinia), results showed that crop management involving legume-wheat rotations produced higher grain yields on durum wheat, while tillage had no significant effect under rotational systems. In contrast, continuous wheat cultivation with conventional tillage produced the lowest grain yields that were also less stable.

It was revealed that the main environmental indicator for grain yield is rainfall patterns. Rainfall after heading was crucial for grain yields with conventional tillage, while rainfalls before heading are more important for conservation tillage management and especially for sod seeding which helps conserve soil moisture.

3.1.3. Comparison of crop management practices

Rotations & fertilisation

In Slovakia (Borovce long-term experiment) grain yield of winter wheat was affected by crop rotation. Significantly lower grain yield was recorded with the 80 % proportion of cereals in crop rotation compared to 40 % and 60 % proportion of cereals in crop rotation. The type of nutrition presented by combination of mineral fertilizers with organic fertilizer Veget® or solely mineral

fertilization did not show significant impact on grain yield probably due to basic fertility of chernozem in Borovce.

Similarly to grain yield, it was revealed that diverse crop rotation with 40 % proportion of cereals reduced the inter-annual yield variability, and the lowest stable winter wheat grain yield was provided with the 80 % proportion of cereals in crop rotation.

Regarding the impact of weather on grain yield, a positive relationship between grain yield and annual total precipitation was found.

Combined agro-ecological practices as mitigation measures

In Italy (Basilicata), the implementation of agroecological management practices adopted in the flat strips such as the introduction of cover crops, regardless of their management (ploughed in as green manure or flattened by a roller crimper), combined with the application of commercial organic fertilizers enhances the yield energy productivity of the crop sequence. However, these treatments were the most unstable.

In the ridges, the introduction of cover crops combined with the application of organic fertilizers (both commercial fertilizers and on farm-compost) increased crop productivity compared to bare soils without inputs of commercial fertilizers. Nevertheless, no significant differences in yield stability were observed across these treatments.

Interestingly, although the observed differences may not achieve statistical significance, there appears that the inputs of organic fertilizers tend to increase crop productivity both in ridges and flat strips systems, particularly when no cover crops are grown. This trend suggests a hierarchy of productivity levels, with the control treatment yielding the lowest productivity, followed by on-farm compost, and finally commercial fertilizers yielding the highest productivity.

3.2. Crop management, agroecological systems and their influence on crop yield stability : statistical analyses

Table 3 summarizes the statistical results obtained in each LTE. The significance levels of treatments, years and climate are represented per crop and soil/crop management practice.

Table 3. Summary table of statistical results obtained in each LTE

LTes	Comparing	Treatments	Parameter	Statistical results		
				Treatment	Year	Climate
BE-FL	Soil management practices (SMP : slurry, tillage, compost)	SMP in silage maize	Yield	n.s.	***	-
		SMP in potato	Yield	n.s.	***	-
		SMP in spring barley	Yield	***	***	-
		SMP in fodder beet	Yield	n.s.	***	-
		SMP in silage maize	Yield stability	n.s.	*	-
		SMP in potato	Yield stability	n.s.	n.s.	-
		SMP in spring barley	Yield stability	n.s.	*	-
		SMP in fodder beet	Yield stability	n.s.	n.s.	-
BE-WL1 - OM	Soil management practices (SMP : organic matter inputs)	Climate extreme in maize (drought stress vs normal years)	Yield stability	n.s.	-	***
		Climate extreme in winter barley (extreme rainfalls vs normal years)	Yield stability	n.s.	-	**
		SMP in sugar beet	Yield	n.s.	***	-
		SMP in winter wheat	Yield	**	***	-
		SMP in winter barley	Yield	***	***	-
		SMP in sugar beet	Yield stability	n.s.	**	-
		SMP in winter wheat	Yield stability	n.s.	*	-
		SMP in winter barley	Yield stability	n.s.	n.s.	-
		Climate extreme in sugar beet (cold stress vs normal years)	Yield	*	-	n.s.
		Climate extreme in winter wheat (heat stress vs normal years)	Yield	***	-	**
		Climate extreme in winter wheat (drought stress vs normal years)	Yield	***	-	***
		Climate extreme in winter wheat (wet stress vs normal years)	Yield	***	-	***
		Climate extreme in winter barley (heat stress vs normal years)	Yield	***	-	**
		Climate extreme in winter barley (drought stress vs normal years)	Yield	***	-	***
		Climate extreme in sugar beet and winter wheat (various stresses)	Yield stability	n.s.	-	n.s.
Climate extreme in winter barley (heat stress vs normal years)	Yield stability	n.s.	-	***		
Climate extreme in winter barley (drought stress vs normal years)	Yield stability	n.s.	-	*		
BE-WL2 - Tillage	Soil & Crop management practices (tillage & fungicides)	Tillage in sugar beet	Yield	n.s.	***	-
		Tillage in winter wheat	Yield	n.s.	n.s.	-
		Crop protection in winter wheat	Yield	***	n.s.	-
		Tillage in sugar beet	Yield stability	n.s.	n.s.	-
		Tillage in winter wheat	Yield stability	n.s.	***	-
		Crop protection in winter wheat	Yield stability	n.s.	-	-
		Climate extreme in sugar beet (heat stress vs normal years)	Yield	n.s.	-	*
		Climate extreme in sugar beet (heat stress vs normal years)	Yield stability	n.s.	-	n.s.

CH	Farming systems (org. vs conv.) & Crop management practises (level of fertilisation)	Farming systems in potatoes	Yield	**	n.s.	n.s.
		Farming systems in winter wheat	Yield	**	n.s.	n.s.
		Farming systems in maize	Yield	**	n.s.	n.s.
		Farming systems in soybean	Yield	*	n.s.	n.s.
		Farming systems in winter wheat (half fert.)	Yield stability	*	-	-
		All other treatments	Yield stability	n.s.	-	-
IT-Basilicata	MITIORG field trial - Climate Change Adaptation and Mitigation Measures in Organic Vegetable Systems	Cover crops management x Organic fertilisation – in Flat strip	Yield stability	multivariate analyses based on AMMI, and GGE		
		Introduction of cover crops x Organic fertilisation - in ridge	Yield stability	multivariate analyses based on AMMI, and GGE		
IT-Sardinia Ussana	Soil & crop management practices (tillage, crop rotations)	Tillage management	Yield	n.s.	***	-
		Monocropping (durum wheat) vs crop rotations (durum wheat - grain legumes)	Yield	***		-
		Tillage management x rotations	Yield	**		-
IT-Sardinia Ussana	Soil & crop management practices (tillage, crop rotations)	Tillage management x rotations	Yield stability	multivariate analyses based on AMMI, GGE and PLS regression		
		Tillage management	Yield	n.s.	***	-
		Monocropping (durum wheat) vs crop rotations (durum wheat - grain legumes)	Yield	***		-
		Tillage management x rotations	Yield	***		-
SK	Crop management practices (rotations & type of fertilisation)	Proportion of cereals in crop rotations	Yield	*	-	*
		Fertilisation (mineral fertilizers vs combination of mineral and organic fertilizers)	Yield	n.s.	-	*
		Proportion of cereals in crop rotations	Yield stability	*	-	-
		Fertilisation (mineral fertilizers vs combination of mineral and organic fertilizers)	Yield stability	*	-	-

Legend

***	< 0.001
**	< 0.01
*	< 0.05

4. Identification of soil related drivers of yield stability in specific AE systems

Soil related drivers of yield stability and thus an evaluation of farming system performance with respect to the long-term performance was performed in detail at the Swiss DOK LTE, where organic and conventional farming systems are compared. Multivariate adaptive regression

spline models (MARS) were used to identify non-linear relationships between environmental, agronomic, and management factors on yield fluctuations. Fertilization factors such as mineral nitrogen fertilization and the climate variables had a much larger effect on yields than soil properties had. Among soil properties, soil organic carbon (SOC) content provided the strongest explanation of yield variability for potatoes and maize with a significant positive effect on yields. In detail, crop yields of potatoes are predicted to increase with increasing soil organic carbon (SOC) concentrations until a threshold of 0.97 %. After that, increases in soil organic carbon concentrations did not affect yields any further. Since means of the observed farming system ranged between 1.1 and 1.26%, this threshold can be interpreted as critical limit, where soils with lower concentrations had significantly lower yields. For maize yields, a strict positive trend was observed after a threshold of 1.14 % of SOC. For winter wheat, total soil N content played the largest role for predicting yield after a minimum concentration of 0.139 %. Since soil N stocks could only be maintained over a period of 35 years in the organically managed systems with full (Fig. 2), the active management of also longer persisting soil properties such as soil N stocks seem both feasible and necessary for improve the system performance. At the same time, this initiates potential trade-off situations, where decisions need to be made between the maintenance of soil N stock and potential N losses to other environmental compartments (Oberson et al., 2024).

Fig. 2, Soil surface N budget vs soil N stock changes over a period of 35 years at the DOK LTE comparing organic (BIOORG) and conventional (CONFYM) farming systems at normal (2) and halved (1) fertilization rates. Numbers above data points indicate the nutrient use efficiency for each farming system. Figure is published in Oberson et al., 2024.

5. General discussion and conclusions

The results and conclusions drawn from the individual reports of the ARTEMIS project partners support the hypothesis that some agroecological practices have the potential to enhance the productivity and resilience of agroecosystems under climatic stress. However, it is important to acknowledge that these results are highly context-specific and occasionally contradictory at European scale, making it challenging to formulate general conclusions from these case-studies. Variations in pedoclimatic conditions across the sites, as well as the diverse types and implementation methods of soil and crop management practices, the category and species of agricultural crops (such as vegetables in MITIORG versus arable crops in the other LTEs), and the specifics of crop rotations, contribute to this complexity. Additionally, the duration of the LTEs is important, as treatment effects are expected to become more pronounced as the LTEs age.

Despite these challenges, similarities can be identified in effects of soil and crop management practices across the LTEs. Under normal climatic conditions, crop rotation diversification exhibited a significant positive impact on yield levels both in Sardinia (Ussana and Benatzu sites) and in Slovakia (Borovce site). In Sardinia, optimal productivity was achieved through crop management strategies that integrated rotations between durum wheat and grain legumes, as opposed to continuous wheat cultivation. In Borovce, the highest winter wheat yields were obtained in more diversified crop rotations, characterized by lower proportions of cereals.

Organic fertilization generally yielded positive effects on productivity across three experiments (LTE-OM, BOPACT, MITIORG), although it was not significant in Borovce. It is important to note that the effects of the tested treatments are highly dependent on various factors, including soil types, organic amendments/fertilizers types (cattle, pig slurry, farmyard manure, on-farm compost, commercial organic fertilizers), their composition, as well as the timing and frequency of their application. The effects were also found to be crop-specific.

The different tillage methods showed not significant effects in Northern Europe (Belgium; BOPACT and LTE-Tillage), whereas positive impacts were obtained in Southern Europe (Sardinia; Ussana and Benatzu) in interaction with crop rotations. Durum wheat yields were notably higher under conservative tillage practices (sod seeding and reduced tillage) compared to conventional tillage within legume-wheat rotations.

The introduction of cover crops resulted in increased yield levels in Italy (MITIORG), whereas this practice did not yield significant results in Belgium (LTE-OM).

Only the Swiss site (DOK) allowed for the comparison of farming systems (conventional versus organic). It appeared that conventional farming consistently achieved higher yield for most of the crops such as potatoes, maize and winter wheat compared to organic systems.

Generally, the effect sizes related to soil and crop management practices on yield stability were smaller than on crop productivity. In the DOK trial, yields were more stable in conventional systems, especially for potatoes, maize, and at half fertilisation level. This suggests that organic

systems are more capable of closing the yield gap under conditions of less severe nutrient limitations.

In Slovakia and Sardinia, treatments that enhanced yields were also exhibited greater stability, in contrast to findings from the MITIORG experiment. In Belgium (BOPACT, LTE-MO and Tillage), no treatment was noted to significantly impact yield stability.

The response of crop yields to climatic stress events was inconsistent and highly dependent on local conditions. During dry cropping seasons, yields were adversely affected in the DOK trial across all crops, with the exception of winter wheat. Similarly in the BOPACT trial, drought showed negative effects for maize yield. Conversely, drought positively influenced winter wheat and barley yields in LTE-OM.

Excessive rainfalls negatively impacted yields of sugar beet and winter wheat in LTE-OM, as well as spring barley in BOPACT, while positively influencing winter wheat yields in Borovce. In Sardinia, durum wheat yields were contingent upon precipitations around the heading stage and of the applied tillage method.

Under climatic stress, organic systems in DOK still underperformed relative to conventional systems, whereas in LTE-OM, organic fertilisation allowed to achieve relative higher yields for winter barley.

The results from the other experiments did not allow us to draw conclusions about the effects of climate on crop yield in relation to management practices. In fact, a major limitation encountered in most experiments was the relatively small number of observations with climatic stress events, particularly in more recent experiments or those where only one crop was cultivated each year.

Furthermore, it is important to contextualize these results, as the impact of soil and crop management practices can be substantial for certain crops within rotations rather than uniformly across all crops. As a perspective, future research should focus on assessing the effects of AE systems across entire crop rotations and on larger scales than those represented by LTEs.

6. List of available country specific reports (see appendices)

6.1. Northern Belgium (Gent, Flanders)

6.2. Southern Belgium (Gembloux, Wallonia)

6.3. Western Switzerland (Therwil, Bâle-Campagne)

6.4. Southern Italy (Metaponto, Basilicata)

6.5. Western Italy (Sardinia)

6.6. Western Slovakia (Piešťany, Trnava)

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